

THE CATEGORY OF EMOTIVITY AS A LINGUISTIC CONCEPT AND MAIN APPROACHES TO ITS STUDY

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Abstract:

This article is dedicated to the problem of studying the category of emotivity. This concept is considered from various viewpoints, and its main characteristics, methods of study, and functions of emotivity are explored. Linguistic and psycholinguistic approaches to its study are examined.

Key words: emotivity, emotions, concept, emotiology

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The category of emotivity is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. For the study of emotivity, the methodological position is that reality is reflected in language in such forms that correlate with both logical and sensory cognition of the world. Therefore, the epistemology of emotivity involves establishing the specifics of the re emotional reflection as an element of objective reality in linguistic signs and their meanings.

The methods being studied to describe emotivity are generally one-sided, as they do not account for the results of other methods. Therefore, we can say that the category of emotivity requires a multidisciplinary approach using diverse methods. Approaching the study of the category of emotivity from different perspectives will provide a comprehensive picture of emotivity, which is currently lacking in linguistics.

The category of emotivity is a psychological, speech, and linguistic phenomenon. This work analyses The analysis of various concepts of emotivity allows us to identify several main directions of its study. According to some linguists, emotional elements should be considered "vague, variable phenomena," extralinguistic in nature [5, p.197]. According to this viewpoint, emotions are expressed only non-conceptually (through rhythm, intonation, prosody). Authors of lexicocentric theories of emotivity recognize lexical units as the main exponents of emotions and classify them into emotive lexeme classes.

According to the "communicative concept of emotivity," emotivity is a polystatus functional-semantic category expressed through a wide range of lexical and grammatical means.

However, the abovementioned approaches are limited and do not provide a complete understanding of the text emotivity category in its broad sense. The limitation of these approaches is due to the fact that their proponents operate solely with linguistic units and categories to describe phenomena that require psycholinguistic analysis.

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The fundamental difference between linguistic and psycholinguistic approaches to the study of the text emotivity lies in the differences in the units operated by linguistics and psycholinguistics [Nosenko, Starodubtseva, 1989: 54].

V.I. Shakhovsky considers emotivity to be a semantic characteristic of language units. According to the linguist, emotivity is characteristic of both language and speech, thus making speech activity emotive and thought emotional when the dominant component is emotional [11, p. 103]. However, researchers such as T. Van Dijk and I.V. Arnold regard emotivity as a characteristic of the text [1, p. 117].

There are also different viewpoints regarding the functions of the category of emotivity. A.B. Kunin speaks of the expressive function of emotivity, defining it as "emotionality in linguistic reflection, that is, a sensuous evaluation of the object and the expression of feelings, moods, and experiences of a person through linguistic or speech means" [6, p. 149].

However, T.A. Van Dijk, I.I. Sandomirskaya, and V.A. Maslova adhere to a different viewpoint: they identify the function of eliciting a specific emotional reaction and state in the recipient. According to this view, emotivity is a kind of subjective experience processed by consciousness with the help of linguistic signals and causing an emotional reaction to the object of depiction. On the other hand, emotivity is a linguistic category encompassing only those emotional phenomena related to the expression of an emotional evaluative attitude, aimed at creating emotional resonance in the listener [8, 10].

Bally Ch. believed that the expression of emotions is the central function of language. In his opinion, emotive components exist on all these levels, which is confirmed by modern research [2, p. 43].

In philology, emotivity is understood as "an optional emotional component of meaning, recognizing that purely linguistic approaches and methods of research are not applicable to this phenomenon" [3, p. 66].

In the nineties of the nineteenth century, a new paradigm of linguistic research emerged - cognitive linguistics. One of the main tasks is "the study of mental processes of natural language processing: building a model of its understanding, its perception, and its production" [9, p. 35].

Within the framework of the cognitive paradigm, since the eighties, the linguistics of emotions "emotiology" has been developed. The area of research - the emotivity of language, speech, and text - determines the fundamentality, theoretical and practical significance of linguistic works carried out in this direction, and the global nature of their prospects. Thus, emotiology becomes one of the leading areas of traditional linguistics. The task of emotiology is to study the subjective components of the meaning of units of language, as well as to form and structure knowledge about the emotive code of language [4, p. 5].

This science deals with the study of the linguistic reflection of emotions, both as a mental essence and as a real phenomenon of reality or as a form of subject's assessment of an external world object [7, p. 47].

It should be noted that emotiology combines cognitive psychology and linguistics. Research in emotiology uses knowledge about emotions obtained in other areas, in particular, data from cognitive science, on the basis of which a linguistic concept of emotions is being developed. Therefore, many linguists define emotiology

as the science of verbalization, expression, and communication of emotions [11, p. 49-52].

Linguistics investigates both verbal and non-verbal expressions of emotion. According to some scholars, there is no emotional component in the structure of language, and that there is no emotional lexicon in language. Other scholars somewhat absolutize the emotional component of a statement, paying great attention to it. They believe that any statement is emotional. In their view, an emotionally neutral style does not exist. V.G. Gak adheres to this latter viewpoint. In his works, while analyzing the emotional aspect of a statement, he paid attention to emotions and assessments [9, p. 35].

Therefore, the category of emotivity is a complex phenomenon. There are many approaches and diverse points of view regarding what emotivity is, to which component of lexical meaning it belongs. Therefore, it can be said that the problem of studying the category of emotivity is one of the complex and relevant problems of modern linguistics.

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